

ENVIRONMENTAL DURABILITY OF F/A-18 GR/EP COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An environmental durability trial is being conducted on F/A-18 gr/ep composites at five tropical test sites in Australia and Malaysia. Two types of specimen have been exposed in the external tropical environment for periods of up to 9 years and measurements have been made of moisture absorption levels, fatigue durability and residual strength. The maximum level of moisture absorption recorded has been 0.7 wt%. Sandwich beam specimens representative of aircraft structure, containing different types of damage or simulated repairs, have withstood over 10^6 fatigue cycles at close to nominal design limit load in the tropical environment. This result indicates that F/A-18 composite structure should be very durable under long term tropical conditions.

INTRODUCTION

Accelerated environmental testing of materials is commonly used to enable tests within a short time frame. However, it is often found that accelerated testing does not reveal the true long-term behaviour, or even provide the correct ranking of candidate materials. Also, many compromises are inherent in accelerated test procedures, meaning that fully realistic test conditions are often not used. For example, it is not realistic to examine the combined influence of UV radiation, varying humidity levels, wind speed (changing convective heat transfer conditions) and alternating load conditions on the mechanical properties of composite materials. During real environmental exposure of aircraft structure, it is likely that these influences will combine to provide actual conditions very different from those commonly used in test laboratories. For these reasons a long-term environmental trial is being conducted on graphite/epoxy (gr/ep) composites using actual tropical test conditions. The material system chosen for this trial is the same as that used in the F/A-18 aircraft, which has approximately 34% of its external surface constructed from gr/ep. Although other countries such as America Canada and Spain also operate this aircraft, Australia has unique climatic conditions, including high levels of humidity in the tropics, low temperatures at high altitude over northern Australia, and intense sunlight.

The aims of the program were a) to determine the equilibrium moisture absorption level of the composite material, b) to examine the environmental durability of the materials used (including paint finishes and sealants) with representative damage or repairs, and c) to investigate the influence of exposure location and type on the environmental durability. This information is necessary a) to assess the need to dry out aircraft components prior to repair, and assess any residual strength degradation due to moisture absorption and its interaction with pre-existing

damage, b) to indicate the need for any preventative maintenance actions should the material systems be found to be significantly degraded by the exposure conditions and c) to permit assessment of the best options for the storage of aircraft and aircraft components on bases, for example, and hence to decide if aircraft shelters are necessary to avoid significant degradation of components. Another aim was to examine the influence of typical environmental conditions on the durability of the types of minor repairs that will be performed on actual aircraft components under field conditions.

The experimental program involves two specimen types exposed at five locations in Australia and Malaysia. The trial has been under way for more than eight years and this report provides some of the results obtained part way through the program. Equilibrium moisture levels for the exposure site in Malaysia indicate that the moisture absorbed is less than the 1% commonly assumed in laboratory trials, and appears to be unaffected by the type of exposure to sunlight. There is no consistent effect of environmental exposure on the interlaminar shear strength of the materials studied, and the durability of structural detail specimens under combined fatigue loading and tropical exposure conditions has been excellent.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The trial involves the exposure of two types of specimens to tropical environments at five sites in Australia and Malaysia. The main exposure site is the Aeronautical and Maritime Research Laboratory (AMRL) tropical test facility at Innisfail in the far north of Queensland (AMRL-Q) and the others are Royal Australian Air Force (RAAF) bases at Williamtown, NSW, Tindal and Darwin in the Northern Territory, and Butterworth in Malaysia. Both specimen types are made from Hercules AS4/3501-6 gr/ep pre-preg.

Figure 1. Schematic diagram of loading rig.

The first specimen is a gr/ep-skinned, aluminium honeycomb sandwich beam in which the ten ply skins [(±45,0,90,0)s lay-up] are bonded to the core with FM-300 adhesive. The beam specimens are loaded in four-point bending in nine ladder rigs containing 12 specimens each. The general arrangement of the loading rigs is shown in Fig. 1. A hydraulic ram in each rig is used to load all 12 specimens cyclically from a minimum of 200 microstrain ($\mu\epsilon$) to a maximum peak strain of either 2500, 2750 or 3000 $\mu\epsilon$ tension or compression. The specimens receive the first 5 blocks of 100,000 cycles at 2500 $\mu\epsilon$ and then the load is increased to apply 2750 $\mu\epsilon$ for a further 2.5 blocks of 100,000 cycles and the final 2.5 blocks are at 3000 $\mu\epsilon$. After each 100,000 cycle block the beams are removed from the ladder rigs. Each beam is then subjected to 40 overload cycles at 3500 $\mu\epsilon$ in an Instron test machine. Ultrasonic C-scanning¹ is then performed to check for damage growth followed by thermal cycling between -50°C and +104°C. The beams are then replaced in the rigs for another block of 100,000 load cycles. The objective of the load and temperature cycles and the tropical exposure is to simulate as closely as possible (within the limits of this simple system) the actual conditions which RAAF aircraft will experience during operation.

Compliance measurements using bonded strain gauges² are automatically taken from the beams during cycling and are used to provide an indication that damage growth may have occurred.

C-scanning is then used to quantify any delamination growth. The beams are of five different types:

1. Undamaged
2. Artificial delamination (circular PTFE inclusions included in the gr/ep skin to simulate delamination)
3. Impact damage (by dropped weight onto the gr/ep skin prior to bonding to the core)
4. Impact damage (onto the beam after the skin is bonded to the core)
5. Simulated repairs.

The PTFE inclusions were either 5, 15 or 25 mm in diameter and were included between the second and third plies of the skin. The impact damage was produced by a dropped-weight impactor with energy levels from 0.3 to 2 joules. This damage was characterised by ultrasonic C-scanning prior to starting the trial. The damaged skin of the beam is loaded in compression and, to investigate if there is any influence of direct exposure to ultra-violet (UV) radiation on the response of the beams, there is an equal number of beams with the compression face upwards exposed to sunlight as those with the damage facing downwards. The sandwich-beam specimens are closely representative of the structure found in both the speedbrake and stabilator of the F/A-18.

The repair specimens are shown schematically in Fig. 2. Apart from the repair itself, the dimensions and other properties of the beams shown in Fig. 2 are identical to those of the other four types. Repairs were applied to both faces of each beam to increase the number of experimental results and to ensure the loads in the repaired regions were symmetrical. Single-sided repairs will have a neutral axis offset and, if damage should occur during the loading, the stress state would be complex and difficult to analyse. These repair beams closely represent actual repairs to aircraft structure as it is likely that such repairs will be supported by both the substructure of the component and the surrounding structure. The repair beams were manufactured using four different methods;

1. The baseline condition in which precured patches were bonded under autoclave conditions to a dry sandwich beam specimen
2. A precured patch bonded under optimum vacuum bag conditions to a partially moisturised sandwich beam specimen
3. A cocured patch bonded under optimum vacuum bag conditions to a dry sandwich beam specimen
4. A cocured patch bonded under optimum vacuum bag conditions to a partially moisturised sandwich beam specimen.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of a repaired beam. The dark area is the damaged region which has been removed and filled with a plug of FM-300 adhesive. The repair patches are bonded with FM-300 adhesive. The diagram is not to scale.

The level of moisture chosen for the beams was 0.4 wt% as this had been shown in previous tests to give rise to significant levels of voiding in the bondline and cocured plies during the cure cycle. The aim of these tests was to simulate real repairs which are likely to be performed on aircraft components in the field where autoclave processing is unavailable and incomplete drying of components is typical. The specimens were painted and the honeycomb protected from corrosion by a polysulphide sealant.

The second specimen type is a moisture absorption coupon, 20 plies thick, with a $(\pm 45, 0, 90, 0)_{s_2}$ lay-up. The coupons are twice as thick as the skins of the sandwich beam specimens and are designed to simulate the moisture absorption characteristics of the beam skins. Sandwich beam skins absorb moisture from only one side and the coupons were made twice the thickness to compensate for absorption from both sides. They are located in a stainless steel fixture in such a way that all specimens experience the prevailing levels of humidity but experience three different degrees of exposure to solar radiation. Specimens classed as “exposed” are fully exposed to solar radiation during the day, “protected” specimens are fully protected from direct incident radiation by a stainless steel plate, while “shaded” specimens are placed beneath a piece of aluminium honeycomb which restricts direct exposure to radiation to only a few hours at midday. Half of all the specimens for each of these three conditions are painted, while the remainder are unpainted. The paint used was the same as that applied to the F/A-18 aircraft and consisted of a two-part epoxy polyamide anti-corrosive primer and a two-part aliphatic polyurethane enamel finishing coat. This same paint scheme is also used on the beam specimens. Four coupons of each type were weighed regularly and the results averaged.

Half of the moisture absorption coupons have been returned to AMRL and sectioned to allow interlaminar shear strength (ILS) tests to be performed. The testing is as per ASTM method D 2344-84 with a specimen length of 12mm and width of 10 mm. The central section of each coupon which remains after the ILS specimens are cut out, is dried to constant weight at 80°C to determine accurately the overall level of moisture absorbed by each coupon.

Further details of the experimental method are given in. ³

RESULTS

The weight changes experienced by the coupons at the Butterworth exposure site are shown in Fig. 3. Plotted in this figure are the average results for the painted coupons over the last 9 years, together with the result for the unpainted exposed coupons. Note that the moisture absorption coupons were naturally conditioned in the AMRL laboratory to a moisture content of 0.3% before the trial began. The final weight change associated with drying the coupons to constant weight at AMRL is plotted in the top right hand corner of the graph. From this result it is clear that the actual moisture content of the protected coupons correlates closely with their total weight change. Applying this result to the other bases allows estimates to be made of the total moisture absorbed at each location by the protected specimens, Table 1.

The ILS specimens were tested under four conditions: a) as received, tested at 20°C; b) as received, tested at 100°C; c) dried to constant weight, tested at 20°C and d) dried to constant weight, tested at 100°C. Only the first of these test conditions will be reported on in this paper.

Table 1. *Equilibrium moisture absorption levels and selected meteorological data for the exposure sites.*

	Exposure Site				
	Butterworth	Darwin	Tindal	Williamtown	AMRL-Q
Equilibrium Moisture Level	0.74	0.7	0.45	0.65	0.7
Daily Mean Relative Humidity	81%		53%		83%
Daily Mean Temperature °C	27.3		26.7		24

Figure 3. Weight changes for selected coupons exposed at Butterworth. Also included in the top right hand corner are the corresponding moisture levels determined by drying the coupons to constant weight. These data points are superimposed at a level of 0.74%.

Two coupons for each exposure condition (e.g., unpainted, shaded condition at Butterworth) were sectioned to provide 24 individual ILS specimens. This allows six specimens to be tested for each of the four test conditions. The data for four of the exposure sites are summarised in Table 2. The sample means and variances are given for all the test conditions and are compared to the baseline condition specimen. This is a panel which had been held at AMRL for the duration of the trial and has been sectioned recently into test coupons for ILS testing. This panel has conditioned naturally in the laboratory over the last nine years and has approximately 0.7% moisture content. It has never been exposed to UV radiation and, as such, provides a control against which the other coupons can be tested. The statistical test which has been applied to the means in Table 2 is a *t*-test assuming unequal variances. The difference between the control and sample means has been evaluated at the 95% confidence level and statistically significant differences are identified in Table 2 with a tick. The variances are compared by using the F test and again differences are compared at the 95% level. When all the experimental data have been collected for this trial, a complete three-factor analysis of variance will be performed to investigate the dependence of residual strength (both ILS and flexural) on the exposure site, the surface treatment of the coupons, and the type of exposure.

A qualitative result concerning the painted coupons is that the paint scheme has exhibited extremely good durability. This paint was applied in the manufacturing facility used in the construction of the Australian F/A-18 aircraft and is fully representative of the paint found on the RAAF aircraft. After at least eight years of direct exposure to solar radiation, no significant cracking or flaking of the paint has been found on any of the exposure coupons and the overall adhesion of the paint and primer system to the composite has been excellent. Under an optical microscope at a magnification of 60 times, slight surface cracks are visible in some of the exposed and shaded coupons, however, these do not extend completely through the paint film and had not caused any disbonding of the film. The only obvious degradation of the paint films is a slight fading of the colour and this is noticeable only because the very end of each specimen is held by a stainless steel clip which protects this part from UV radiation. The unpainted specimens have obviously lost the surface layer of resin due to UV degradation and this is quite noticeable under microscopic examination where loose fibres are clearly visible on the surface.

It is not possible in the space available to include graphs of the compliance of the beam specimens plotted against the number of cycles. Long-term changes in compliance of 5% or more are taken

to indicate that growth of the pre-existing damage may be occurring in a specimen. Such changes are not observed and ultrasonic C-scanning has not detected any evidence of damage growth.

Table 2. A comparison of the means and variances for the ILS tests conducted at 20°C. Exp denotes exposed specimens, Shd shaded and Prot protected specimens. U stands for unpainted and P for painted. A tick means that the result of the test was significant at the 95% level.

Site		AMRL Control	Exposure Condition					
			Exp U	Exp P	Shd U	Shd P	Prot U	Prot P
	Mean μ	73.6	65.7	64.9	70.0	69.6	72.8	65.9
Butterworth	Variance s^2	45.0	21.2	19.1	47.6	57.0	27.6	43.1
	Test for μ		✓	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Test for s^2		✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Mean	73.6	75.0	72.4	78.6	77.3	83.3	70.3
Tindal	Variance	45.0	123.9	256.7	75.0	64.1	24.0	81.2
	Test for μ		✗	✗	✗	✗	✓	✗
	Test for s^2		✗	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗
	Mean	73.6	67.3	72.3	82.5	74.9	77.0	78.1
AMRL-Q	Variance	45.0	44.3	78.6	2.0	22.9	11.8	30.8
	Test for μ		✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
	Test for s^2		✗	✗	✓	✗	✗	✗
	Mean	73.6	74.2	70.3	71.7	65.2	67.2	65.8
Williamtown	Variance	45.0	15.7	13.3	21.8	34.6	20.6	10.7
	Test for μ		✗	✗	✗	✓	✗	✓
	Test for s^2		✗	✗	✗	✗	✗	✗

DISCUSSION

The results shown in Fig. 3 indicate that the specimens protected from direct exposure to solar radiation slowly gain weight by absorbing water from the air. The time taken for the moisture content to reach equilibrium is dependent to some extent on the exposure location and may take around five years or more for this skin thickness. Detailed readings taken early in the trial show that the moisture level fluctuates in response to the seasonal variation in the humidity, which can be extreme in locations affected by monsoon activity. These local variations are minor compared with the overall level of moisture absorption. The data in Fig. 3 show a slight weight drop at the last data point, caused by the specimens being washed at the Butterworth base prior to transportation back to AMRL. The slight amount of dust/dirt etc which is removed by the washing causes the weights to drop slightly. The equilibrium moisture absorption levels shown in Table 1 are less than the level of 1% which is commonly used in laboratory trials of gr/ep materials. In this regard the 1% level is conservative. However, it appears that there is little likelihood of 1% moisture absorption ever being reached in the field under the conditions used in this trial.

An interesting result for the exposed and shaded specimens shown in Fig.3 is that they do not record the same weight gains as the protected specimens although they do gain approximately the same amount of moisture. This is due to the competing effects of moisture absorption and surface degradation due to UV radiation. The exposed specimens make only slight weight gains before beginning to lose weight about one year after exposure commences. The shaded specimens increase in weight compared with the exposed specimens but, after four years of exposure, their weight begins to decrease slowly. It is expected that if the trial were to continue the weight loss

associated with this degradation of the paint would accelerate with time. Partial shading by the honeycomb is seen to provide worthwhile protection to the paint scheme (although not complete protection). In this regard some protection for the aircraft would seem to be valuable as the life of the paint scheme would be extended by many years if it were not continually exposed to UV radiation. This conclusion is based only on the data of weight changes and not on a full examination of the paint finishes. However, data such as those shown in Fig. 3 indicate some degradation of the paint after only one year of full exposure. These data also indicate that it is not possible to make accurate conclusions about the amount of absorbed water in coupons during a trial such as this as the competing weight loss due to resin or paint degradation would be very difficult to quantify. The only alternative is to withdraw and dry specimen at periods throughout the trial.

The effect of UV exposure on unpainted specimens is clearly seen in Fig. 3, where the exposed unpainted specimens appear to lose weight almost immediately. This is due to the very rapid degradation of the surface layers of epoxy resin by the UV radiation. These layers are rapidly lost from the specimen after which the rate of weight loss slows. The samples shown in Fig. 3 eventually stabilise, though specimens at other bases showed a slow continuing weight loss caused by the bare surface fibres being removed from the surface by wind and rain exposing fresh resin underneath. The free fibres on the surface are readily observed under an optical microscope. It is therefore important that composite aircraft components be properly stored whenever they are unprotected by a primer or paint finish, and that they should not be exposed outdoors.

Composite components are often repaired with an elevated-temperature-curing adhesive and moisture in the skins can be liberated during the cure to form voids within the adhesive bondline and within the repair plies if they are cocured. This effect has been simulated in the repaired sandwich beam specimens. From this trial it appears that it is necessary to assume only that the component has a moisture content of 0.7% as an input to any moisture drying calculations. Note that this is the moisture content of the composite skins and not the amount of moisture which may have accumulated in the honeycomb core due to small gaps in the structure. Moisture in the core can be estimated only by NDI examination and it will require additional drying time for its removal via the entry path. This form of moisture is also potentially more damaging as incomplete drying prior to repair will give rise to excessive pressures within the core, sufficient to cause a major disbond of the skin from the core. An interesting supplementary result was obtained from an F/A-18 horizontal stabilator which is the subject of a separate program aimed at developing scarf repairs to highly strained structure. This component, which was around eight years old, has been stored in laboratory conditions for the past six years. A section of disbanded skin was removed and dried to constant weight at 80°C in an oven and the moisture content was found to be approximately 0.7% in good agreement with the control coupons naturally conditioned at AMRL.

Table 2 shows that several of the ILS results were statistically significant in comparison with the controls at the 95% level. However, there is no consistent trend in the data. Two of the significant results were from specimens which returned greater mean strengths than the control and the others were not as strong. No consistent effect of exposure type or location is evident. An interesting result is the experimental scatter, which is particularly high for the exposed Tindal specimens. These specimens are also comparatively dry (Table 1) compared with those at the other exposure locations. This could be relevant to any consideration of design allowables for repairs to aircraft stationed at such a base. The remaining moisture absorption coupons will be withdrawn from the exposure sites within twelve months and tested for flexural strength, which should be a more sensitive test for surface degradation than the ILS test. A rigorous analysis of variance will then be applied to all the data to test for statistically significant evidence of degradation. The interim result from the trial to date is that no consistent evidence has been found for degradation in the interlaminar shear strength. This is consistent with the findings of Fukuda⁴ who examined the reduction in ILS strength of gr/ep samples exposed in Japan for three years. Dexter and Baker⁵ observed a slight reduction in ILS strength for unpainted gr/ep samples exposed at six locations world wide for periods up to ten years.

The general strain level associated with the Design Limit Load (DLL) of the composite structure on the F/A-18 is around $2750\mu\epsilon$. The sandwich beam specimens at AMRL-Q have experienced over one million load cycles at strain levels in this range, which represents a very severe test of the material systems. In addition they have experienced hundreds of load excursions to $3500\mu\epsilon$ which is close to the Design Ultimate Load (DUL). DUL represents the most extreme load which the aircraft should be capable of withstanding without failure. An aircraft may typically see such a load only once in its lifetime. Given that these damaged beam specimens have been exposed outdoors in a severe tropical environment during the load cycling, the durability displayed by the specimens is exceptionally high. This result provides confidence in the ability of this type of aircraft structure with representative damage to cause few maintenance difficulties due to environmental exposure. Of equal significance is the durability displayed to date by the repaired beams. The nature of these repairs was to include voids deliberately within the adhesive bondline and in the cocured patches and yet, to date, no evidence of degradation has been found. A third specimen type, in the form of a double overlap strap joint, is being developed to investigate repair performance further. This specimen will allow more quantitative data to be collected from the specimen during cycling so as to define clearly the failure mechanism of repair joints under representative service conditions.

CONCLUSIONS

Equilibrium moisture absorption levels recorded for AS4/3501-6 laminates at five tropical test sites were in the range 0.45 to 0.7%. These values are lower than the level of 1% which is commonly assumed in laboratory trials and provide a valid experimental figure for use in estimates of the time required for drying of moist aircraft components prior to repair. Laminates unprotected by paint rapidly degrade on exposure to UV radiation and shading of aircraft by shelters or hangers is desirable to extend the life of paint schemes. There was generally no consistent degradation of ILS values of laminates due to UV exposure. Sandwich beams representative of aircraft structure with damage and simple repairs, have demonstrated excellent durability under the combined effects of outdoors tropical exposure and cyclic loading to around DLL. This indicates that delaminations up to 25mm in diameter do not cause significant problems with durability in this type of aircraft structure under long term tropical exposure conditions.

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